

The Historical Importance of Chatta Bal Mukund Rai Narnaul :

A Case Study

Nitin

*Research scholar Department of History including AIHC and Archaeology,
H.N.B. Garhwal Central University, Srinagar (Uttarakhand)*
Email: nitinjangir19@gmail.com

Devendra Pratap Yadav

*Research scholar Department of History including AIHC and Archaeology,
H.N.B. Garhwal Central University, Srinagar (Uttarakhand)*

Accepted: 17 June 2023 / Published online: 30 June 2023

Abstract

Chatta Bal Mukund Rai is a mediaeval monument that is protected by the State Archaeology and Museum Department of Haryana. This monument is located in Narnaul city, which is a tehsil of Mahendargarh district. This city is situated on the Trans-Haryana Expressway (NH-152D) road. Narnaul was also closely associated with the Sur-Afghans and the Mughals. Through this paper, we will understand the actual condition of the monument and why it was built at that time. At present, the State Archaeology Department is doing the work of conservation on monuments, so along with this, we will also do a comparative study of before and after conservation.

Key Words: Monument, Hamam, Chatta, Conservation, cascade, medieval.

Introduction

The city of Narnaul is situated in the south of Haryana province, and there are many ancient buildings inside this city. An important dynasty rose to power in 1526 AD after the fall of the Sur dynasty in northern India, and the city of Narnaul was under the control of the Mughal dynasty at that time. Because Narnaul is the centre of trade, that's why the rulers built Sarai and palaces here. Chatta Mukund Rai is a building built by Lala Mukund Rai, which today comes under Haryana State Archaeology and Museum. Built in 1628–1658 AD, the Chatta was the palace of Rai Bal Mukund Das, a resident of Narnaul who served as Superintendent of Grants for the Mughal emperor Shah Jahan. In local parlance, this building is called Birbal ka Chatta. Lala Rai Mukund was a mansabdar during the reign of Shah Jahan (Parihar 1985:45).

Location-

Narnaul is certain from three side by Alwar district of Rajasthan on west, south and east, Delhi on the northeast. Narnaul is about 141 km from national capital Delhi. Narnaul is located on Trans-Haryana Expressway (NH-152D) road. Generally the monuments is located in the centre of the city. Co-ordinates of the Monument is 28°04'52" N 76°10'85" E .

The district is a plain area with the perennial Krishnawati/Kasaunti or Dohan River on its middle and north areas, which have formed its flood plain area on the north (Mehra 2013:145).

Origin of the Area

Narnaul Tehsil is very rich in cultural and monumental things. The history of the tehsil starts with Maharishi Bhrigu. Bhrigu left his son in Dhoshi Hill in Narnaul and migrated to Bharuch (GJ). Maharishi Chyavan established an ashram on Dhoshi Hill. Over the years, this place has been an important centre of Jainism; Adinatha, Parsvanatha, and Tirthankarnath sculptures are found in this area (Dangi 2017: 318-320, Mahendargarh district Gazetteer, 1988:38). After that, the Anangapal Tomara and his cousin established Narnaul town to rule this area and the Raja Laun Karan seat near the Dhoshi hill. The name of the town has been derived differently: Nahar-Nual, or the "Forest of Tigers," or Nar-Naul, or "beautiful women." Perhaps it contained beautiful women and Nag-Naul, named after a snake and mongoose that were seen fighting when the city was founded (Mahendargarh district Gazetteer 1988:37). The town later fell into Rathor Rajput's hands, and subsequent to that, in AD 1137, a Muslim saint warrior, Hazrat Turkman, popularly known as Shah Wilayat, is said to have come to Narnaul with jewels in one hand and a sword in the other. He fought many battles with the native Rathor Rajputs but was killed during one such fight. A tomb and a mosque, later built, still stand in the town (ASI 2009:35). After the death of Shihab-ud-din

Guri, Qutb-ud-din Aibak Guri became the new general of his area, and this area came under Turkish rule. After Aibak, Iltutmish paid attention to this area and divided it into iqta. Each iqta is under the direct control of the Sultan. The Tughlaqs, Sayyides, and Lodis tried to direct control to this area, and Bahlol Lodi gave this jagir to Ibrahim Khan Sur, the great-grandfather of Sher Shah Suri. When the second Afghan kingdom came, Sher Shah Suri built a very magnificent mausoleum at Narnaul on the grave of his grandfather, Ibrahim Khan Suri. Sher Shah divided his kingdom into sixty-six Sarkar, and Mahendargarh comes under the Narnaul Sarkar (INTACH Haryana 2016:15). But Akbar changed this administration system; Sarkar is now known as Mahal, and in Ain-i-Akbari, he told us about this. In 1672, when Aurangzeb was the ruler of India, a petty quarrel near Narnaul between a Satnami cultivator and a Mughal foot soldier of the local revenue collector led to the rebellion. Gradually, this matter has increased. When Aurangzeb knew about this, he sent there a large force under Radanaz Khan. The rebellion was thus crushed and the affected areas brought under control. In 1750, the Rao's of Rewari and Raja Madho Singh of Jaipur seized a sizeable territory in the district around Narnaul and Kanaud. The battle of Narnaul was undoubtedly one of the most decisive battles of the Uprising of 1857. After the battle, Tula Ram moved into Rajasthan and joined Tantya Tope's forces for one year. After India achieved independence, the Mahendargarh district, along with the other districts of the Patiala State, formed part of the Patiala and East Punjab State Union in 1948, which merged with Punjab in 1956. Haryana was carved out of Punjab in 1966, and Mahendargarh became the district of the new state (Mahendargarh district gazetteer 1988:51–55; Yadav 2002:173–176).

Origin of the monument

After the defeat of the Lodi's in the First Battle of Panipat (1526 AD), the Mughal ruler, Babur laid the foundation of the dynasty in India. Due to the location of Narnaul not far from Delhi, this entire area came under the control of the Mughals. Since Narnaul is the centre of regional activities, the rulers built Sarai and palaces here. Whenever a ruler went from Delhi to Ajmer or any part of Rajasthan, this city used to come in between. Royal people used to rest here in these monuments, were also the residence of the local ruler or zamindar of the region. The rulers of this dynasty have made significant contributions in the fields of art and architecture. Many monuments in the Mughal style, a mixture of the Sur-Afghan and Mughal styles developed during the Mughal period, were built during this reign. The city of Narnaul is situated in the south of Haryana province, and there are many ancient buildings inside this city.

About the Monument Rai Bal Mukund ka Chatta (Birbal ka Chatta)

Chatta Bal Mukund Rai is one of the many beautiful buildings built during the medieval period in Narnaul which is a protected monument by the Archaeological Department of Haryana. The literal meaning of “Chatta” is “a honeycomb,” meaning a beautiful abode (Parihar 1985 :45). There are many advantages to this building. The main door of the monument is in the western direction, and the stairs from the door lead directly to a terrace on the first floor (Parihar1985 :45)

Fig1: inside part of Chatta a vertical view of monument

Fig 2: Satellite Mapping of Chatta Rai Bal Mukund Das, Narnaul, provided by State Archaeological museum department, Chandigarh.

There is a main entrance on this floor, which faces west. Its ceiling is adorned with attractive stalactite designs. This gateway leads to a courtyard with deep arches all around and a raised platform in the centre. From this courtyard, one can reach all the other floors, including the ground floor, which has dark, cold, and fragrant rooms, one of which is called the Hamam. The ceilings of most of the rooms were made of wood, which is why most of them collapsed a long time ago. Parts of the building bear traces of painted decoration. The haveli is a magnificent five-storied structure consisting of halls, terraces, and rooms around a central courtyard. The realisation of graceful arches and terraces at different levels adorned with open pavilions and balconies adds to the beauty of the building.

Although the building originally had three underground floors, presently only one level is accessible. Remains of an elaborate cooling water system can be observed in the basement. The large "Tehkhana" (underground room for use in hot summers) has clay pipes for running well water around its walls to create a cooling effect in the "Tehkhana." The roof line is dotted with uneven, airy pavilions and open terraces to catch the breeze (Vardhan: 19-20). In close proximity

to the Chatta is the Sarai, built by Rai Bal Mukund Das to provide transit resting facilities to the caravans passing through Narnaul during the 17th century AD.

This building is being protected today, and Haryana government conservation work is continuing on this protected building. The building was not in a very good state when it was found. We received many of its parts in broken condition. These broken states were preserved by the government. After this, it was found that the building could be developed from the point of view of tourism.

Fig.3: General view of Narnaul city from terrace of Chatta, Photo Courtesy: Mr. Nitin

Fig.4: Before Conservation

Fig.5: After Conservation

An Architecture view

What is currently used as the main gate of the monument is not the original main gate. Earlier this monument was spread over a very long and wide area. When the monument was in good condition in the 17th century, there were other gates around it. The main gate was the Moti Dwar, which is believed to be located at some distance from the monument. But on the basis of its present condition, the gate entering from the west side is considered as the main gate. There is a staircase in front of the west gate which takes us to the first floor of the monument. There is an open terrace on top and a small fountain in the middle.

After going to the first floor, there is a big door to enter inside this monument from the west side (Fig. 6). The top inside of that door is very elaborately designed in the shape of a quadrilateral (Fig.7). To the north of this gate, one can enter through a small door. But perhaps such a small gate is not suitable for such a big monument, and this way is very narrow, so it cannot be the main gate. Probably the main gate of this monument has been broken today. The passage,

which is currently considered to be the main gate, was probably used for women to collect goods from the market and to go directly out of the monument through a secret passage.

Fig.6 : Present main gate at first floor

Fig.7 :internal decorated design after conservation

As mentioned earlier, there are small rooms on two sides of the monuments, in the west and south directions at the Outer wall whose shape is like shops (Fig.10). It is possible that there will be a shop there in which things would be sold here. And one more room also exists, which leads to the well, whose condition has been improved after conservation efforts by the government (Fig.9). If the condition is seen in the earlier place, then it was in very bad condition.

Fig8: Outer wall after conservation Fig9: A shop (probably). Fig 10. the series of shops at the south side.

The walls inside the monument have also been preserved. In this too, changes can be seen after the conservation by the government, the artefacts which existed earlier have been maintained in the same way. In this, we mainly see the big wall outside in the south area and a chhatri which rests completely on the stone pillars (Fig.11). Red and white colour designs were made on the chhatri.

Figure 11: Internal wall before Conservation

Figure 12: Internal wall after Conservation

Its reality remains intact in the present day. Along with this, there were different designs of that wall, whether it was circular or square or reticulated. The designs on the main wall have been made in the same way. The nets which were broken have been reconstructed and installed. Along with this, on going inside, you see big Diwan-e-Aam and Diwan-e-Khas all around.

It is a five-storeyed building having several halls, rooms and pavilions. The liberal use of marble for flooring and pillars in the Diwan-e-Khas (the Central courtyard) adds uniqueness indicating the prosperity of the contemporary Narnaul. The courtyard is located in the middle of the monument, which was constructed by very beautiful marble ornate stones. Marble stones were used which adds to its beauty. There are beautiful halls all around them and a fountain in the middle adds to the beauty of the courtyard.

Fig 13: North Eastern courtyard

Fig14 : Marble Pillars with decoration

On the ground floor of the monument, there are many Hamams. There are also Hamams on the south side, or the mid-area, of the monument. The literary meaning of Hamam is bath, which is underground at this site. There is no way for coming directly Hamam, one can go only stairs from first floor. In the centre is a round tub in the shape of a bathtub with a canopy on top,

Fig.15: Stairs for underground Hamam

Fig.16:internal part of Hamam

Fig.17: A wash room

Fig. 18: 2ndHamam at the mid-area of Chatta

Fig.19:Design for flow water at Cascade to bathtub

with similar figures. Square and Mughal-style figures have been made on the inside wall. In the south of the Hamam, there is a forged skylight, which provides light to the underground bathroom. Water is transported from the well to this spring through a drain, and probably the Muslim women or the Mughal kings and officers who were there used it.

Just as the other part of the monument is beautiful, the same type of beauty is also seen in the ceiling of the monument. Instead of the type of iron gutter used at present, wood was used to make the roofs in the monument. The ceiling has been constructed using large wooden logs. In some parts, the roof is still there, which is proof of its strength. Its wood is currently not available in this area; it might have been brought from another area. Even after all this, it can be seen in the present state of the monument that the wood has been broken and is missing from many parts where it was before. The south wall of the courtyard does not indicate it is breaking naturally, but it is deliberately cut and stolen by someone. Some people intentionally cut the trees. Due to a lack of security, these woods have been stolen. Presently, the security arrangements are made by the government. At present, due to the efforts of the government, efforts are being made to get the wood set again in a particular area and to reconstruct the roofs. Almost all of the North and South Halls have been destroyed. Reconstruction work is in progress, as are some rooms in the west,

Fig.21-22: Wood flat beam, pillar and ceiling Fig.23: Terrace of the monument

where sandstone floors are being laid as before.

There is a very good arrangement of stairs inside the monument—to go down to the Hamam, to enter through the main gate, to go to the underground rooms, to go to the ceiling, etc. To go to the ceiling, there are three stairs, two in the west and one in the east, from the central courtyard that go upward. Along with these stairs, there are also stairs to go down to the side. There are two more rooms on the terrace to the north of the monument, for which a separate set of stairs is made, which are made of stone, with the help of which we can go up to them. After going above them, there are two other small chhatri (Gumbad) as well.

When we enter the monument, first of all, we reach the first floor, but underground rooms have also been made below it. The stairs that go up from the central courtyard have other stairs on their sides that come down to the underground rooms. After going downstairs, when we see two long holes, there are two bathtubs of the same type as those in the Hamam, where water is delivered through pipes made of terracotta. The fountains and springs in the underground chambers were provided to keep them cool during the summer season. In the south,

Fig.24: Series of chhatri at underground Hamam **Fig. 25: A cascade and bathtub, Photo Courtesy: Mr. Nitin**

East corner, there is a well from which water was raised into the apex reservoir by multilevel lifting following the “Persian wheel style” for onward supply of water to the various levels of the building. Fresh water reaches there using drains. These underground rooms are mainly constructed

to escape the hot winds in summer. The temperature outside gets hot during the summer, but the temperature of the underground rooms remained normal. These rooms were used to rest. Secondly, these rooms can also be used as security; according to folklore, there are secret routes from this hive to Jaipur and Delhi.

Conclusion

Now the Chatta Balmukund Rai is under conservation by the Archaeology and Museum Department of Haryana. The monument is protected with modern equipment. Though the local people or government department collected the information and old pictures of the monument, as we have already mentioned, today's monuments are not in complete condition. Monuments have lost a lot of their space, due to which they have been reduced to just a small radius. As we have tried to tell from the satellite image, the actual area required protecting the monument and how much is left today

The conservation work in the southern part is almost on the verge of completion. Conservators try to protect the monument from birds like bats, pigeons, etc. That's why they apply iron grilles to the internal parts of windows. In place of lime stone lattices, similar carvings have been made inside the marble, and they have been placed there, due to which the strength of this structure has doubled and its life has increased even more. All the main features, like wooden art, marble, underground hamams, Diwan a Khas, flower design, fountains, cascades, terracotta pipes, a water well, or Mehrab & Arch, are present here.

Looking at the mediaeval monuments inside the city and its historicity, the city can be declared a historical city, and a new centre of tourism in the south Haryana range can be established here.

Reference

Dangi, V.(2017). *Jainism in Haryana: An Archaeological Perspective*. Heritage: Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies in Archaeology 5.pp. 300-330

District Gazetteer of Mahendargarh, Revenue department Chandigarh, 1988 and 2002.

Yadav, K C.(2002). *Modern Haryana HISTORY and CULTURE*. Manohar publisher and distributors.

Parihar, S.(1985). *Mughal Monuments in the Punjab and Haryana*. Delhi. Inter-India Publication. p. 45.

Jain,S. & Dandona, B.(2012). *Haryana Cultural Heritage Guide*, Edited volume. INTACH, Aryan Book International.

Rahar, J.S.(2001) *Archaeological settlement pattern Of Mahendargarh and Rewari district* (Haryana). Maharishi Dayanand University, Rohtak.

Mehra, G.R.(2013). *Prioritization of sub-watersheds: A case study of Dohan and Krishnawati rivers* . Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra.

